

Kelly Prize

Challenges and opportunities in
synchrotron computed tomography imaging of composites

Yentl Swolfs

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What is computed tomography?

The specific nature of X-ray computed tomography

Getting 3D images = easy

Getting the best possible 3D images efficiently = difficult

What do you need?

A device suited to your needs/material

Suitable software

(Years of) experience

Typical layout of an XCT beamline

The specific nature of synchrotron computed tomography

Mostly parallel beams

- No geometric magnification

- Ample space for load rigs

Voxel size can be smaller

- Not necessarily!

More phase contrast present

- Can be tweaked via propagation distance

Much higher flux

- Faster experiments

- Monochromatic light or pink beam

Three synchrotron techniques

Continuous acquisition

Ultrafast radiography

Holotomography

The ply thickness effect for translaminar fracture toughness

Only one micromechanical model available

Pimenta and Pinho (2014)

The TOMCAT beamline and GigaFRoST detector

800 nm, 2s per scan

Superfast read-out system:
60.000 radiographs in 2 min

Ivanovic et al. (2024)

Miniaturised compact tension specimen

Complex fracture morphology

Detailed pull-out characterisation

Independent 0° cracks

90° cracks ahead of 0° cracks

Fibre breaks near crack tip

Future challenges and opportunities

Challenges:

Unique camera only available at TOMCAT beamline

Fast rig rotations → stability concerns

Opportunities

Swiss Light Source 2.0 upgrade → brighter

2 TOMCAT beamlines

Three synchrotron techniques

Continuous acquisition

Ultrafast radiography

Holotomography

Ultrafast camera

Shimadzu HPV-X2

Up to 10 MHz

Up to 256 frames

250x400 pixels

Setup at FORMAX

High-speed camera

Rotation/translation stages

Specimen degradation

Imaged at 0.1-1 MHz → 256-2560 μs

Degradation due to dose

Degradation due to dose rate

Ultrafast radiography: Future challenges and opportunities

Challenges:

- High enough flux without degrading specimen
- Triggering

Opportunities

- HPV-X3 just launched
- Slower but more sensitive camera alternatives

Three synchrotron techniques

Continuous acquisition

Ultrafast radiography

Holotomography

The basics of holotomography

The benefits of full phase contrast retrieval

Attenuation contrast: $I = I_0 e^{-\mu d}$ (Beer-Lambert law)

μ = attenuation coefficient $\sim Z^4$

d = thickness of material

Phase contrast:

Very sensitive to changes in refractive index

→ Great at matrix-air and air-fibre interface

Setup and load rig at ID16B (ESRF)

Damage development in single-fibre composites

Damage development in glass multi-fibre composites

90% UTS

Holotomography

Future challenges and opportunities

Challenges:

Availability: ESRF ID16B (and potentially PETRA III P05)

Reconstruction

Rigs

Opportunities

Even higher resolutions (50 nm!)

Ptychography (ID16A)

Conclusion

New technique development

- Multidisciplinary work

- Requires beamline scientists

- Specialised rigs

New capabilities

- Enable new insights

- Challenge models

Software needs

- Ultrafast = lots of data

- Reconstruction algorithms

What's next? - Multiprojection imaging

What's next? – X-ray free electron laser (XFEL)

Much brighter than conventional synchrotron light

Contributors

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